

Studies on Pollutants : A New Reagent for the Determination of Nitrite in Water

(Miss) ALKA BHATT and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010 (M.P.)

Manuscript received 24 January 1980, accepted 19 May 1980

A new reagent system is described for the micro determination of nitrites in water. The method is based on the reaction of catechol and micro amount of nitrite in 7-8M acetic acid and coupling the resultant compound with *p*-aminophenol to form a violet coloured solution. It exhibits a wavelength of maximum absorption at 530 nm. The Beer's law is obeyed from 0.6 ppm to 1.6 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be 2.3×10^4 litre mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ and 0.0023 μ g cm⁻² respectively.

NITRITES are regarded as one of the important pollutants present in water. Nitrites are formed in water due to microbial oxidation and reduction of ammonia and nitrate. The increasing use of nitrites in foods, fertilizers, detergents and other industries has caused serious pollution problem. Nitrites are considered as potentially hazardous compounds. Nitrites are suspected to cause cancer¹ due to formation of carcinogenic-N-Nitroso compounds by the reaction with secondary or tertiary amines and amides². They also cause the induction of methemoglobinemia³. The allowable limits of nitrites in potable water as fixed by U.S. Public Health Service is 0.06 ppm⁴. The determination of nitrites in water in micro amounts is necessary with the view point of pollution studies.

Several methods exist for the detection and determination of nitrite in water. The majority of these lack either specificity or sensitivity. The most widely used methods for the determination of nitrite in water are based on the oxidation of nitrite to nitrate⁵⁻⁶, the Griess-Ilosvay diazo-reaction⁷⁻¹⁰ and the colorimetric reaction with amines¹¹. A review of the methods for determination of nitrite is presented by Babko and Pilipenko¹².

In this communication, a new reagent system using catechol and *p*-amino phenol, which has recently been reported¹³ for the detection of oxides of nitrogen in air and water, is described for the determination of nitrites in water. The influence of various experimental parameters such as acidity, temperature, amount of reagent, time for maximum colour development, order of addition of reagent, effect of diverse species on the coloured system have been investigated.

Experimental

Apparatus : ECIL spectrophotometer model GS 865 with 1 cm matched cells, was used for all

measurements. Graduated apparatus of standard calibration were used for measurements.

Reagents :

(a) **Standard sodium nitrite solution :** A stock solution of sodium nitrite was prepared by dissolving 0.15 g of dried A.R. sodium nitrite in 100 ml glass distilled deaerated water. The standard working solution is obtained by diluting 2 ml of this solution to 100 ml. This solution contains 20 μ g nitrite per ml.

(b) **Catechol :** $5 \times 10^{-2}M$ catechol solution was prepared by dissolving 0.55 g of catechol in 100 ml glass distilled water.

(c) ***p*-Amino phenol :** $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ solution was prepared by dissolving 0.11 g of *p*-amino phenol in 100 ml of 0.1 M acetic acid.

(d) **Glacial acetic acid :** 17M glacial acetic acid was used as a reaction medium.

(e) **Solutions of foreign species :** These were prepared from analytical reagent grade chemicals.

All the chemicals used were of Analytical Reagent grade. The solution of catechol and *p*-amino phenol were kept in dark and prepared fresh each week.

Colour reaction :

Catechol reacts with nitrite to form nitroso-catechol¹⁴ in acetic acid medium. The nitroso-catechol couples with *p*-amino phenol to give violet colour¹⁵, which is the basis of this method. This complex is extractable in amyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, and isobutyl ketone.

* Senior author to whom correspondence should be made.

Procedure :

An aliquot of sample solution containing not less than 15 μg and not more than 40 μg nitrite was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask. To it was added 1 ml of catechol and glacial acetic acid and the acidity was maintained $\sim 8M$. The solution was kept for 15 minutes and then 1 ml of *p*-amino phenol was added. Volume was made upto the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of violet coloured solution was measured against the reagent blank prepared under the same condition. The amount of nitrite was deduced from the calibration curve prepared from 15-40 μg of nitrite.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum : The absorption spectrum of the violet coloured species formed by developing colour as described above, was determined in visible region. The absorption spectrum shows that the coloured complex has maximum absorption at 530 nm. The absorbance of the reagent blank was negligible in this region, hence all the measurements were made against distilled water.

Effect of Variables :

Acidity : The wavelength of maximum absorption remains constant from 1-10M acetic acid. Here the acidity was maintained around 7-8M to obtain maximum intensity of the colour. Only acetic acid was found to be suitable for colour development. Other acids change the spectral characteristics and stability of the coloured species.

Effect of time, temperature and reagent concentration : It was observed that at least 15 minutes were required for complete nitrosation and coupling had to be done before 20 minutes after nitrosation. After coupling full colour development takes place in about 45 minutes and is stable for 1 hour.

It was found that the maximum intensity of the colour was obtained at low temperature. The intensity of the colour decreases at higher temperature. Here the temperature was maintained around $20 \pm 2^\circ$. Precaution must be taken that all the measurements are done at the same temperature at which calibration curve is plotted.

The amount of reagent is not critical. For 15-40 μg of nitrite per 25 ml, 1 ml of *p*-amino phenol and 1 ml of catechol solution gave reproducible results.

Order of addition of reagents : It was found that only slight colour developed if catechol was replaced by *p*-amino phenol in the initial reaction.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity and sensitivity :

Beer's law holds good in the range of 15-40 μg of nitrite per 25 ml. The molar absorptivity is $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ lit. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0023 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Influence of foreign species :

In order to assess the possible analytical application of the reaction, the effect of several foreign species, present in water were studied. The foreign species were added to a solution containing 20 μg of nitrite and proceeding as recommended in procedure. The results are summarised in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN SPECIES IN THE DETERMINATION OF NITRITE ION (nitrite 20 μg per 25 ml)

Species	Added as	Amount added mg	Absorbance at 530 nm
None	—	—	0.34
Cl ⁻	NaCl	10	0.34
SO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₄	10	0.335
NO ₃ ⁻	NaNO ₃	2	0.34
IO ₃ ⁻	Na ₃ PO ₄	1	0.34
NH ₄ ⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	2	0.33
SO ₃	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.00
a. SO ₂	"	0.05	0.33
b. Cu ²⁺	Cu(NO ₃) ₂	0.5	0.34
b. Ca ²⁺	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	1	0.345
b. Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄	1	0.34
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	1	0.34
V ⁵⁺	NH ₄ VO ₃	1	0.47
Phenol	as such	40	0.34
Benzene	"	20	0.34
Aniline	"	0.02	0.34
Formaldehyde	"	10	0.33
Nitrobenzene	"	10	0.34
Ethyl alcohol	"	20	0.34
Carbon tetrachloride	"	20	0.34
Chloroform	"	15	0.335
Aldehyde	CH ₃ CHO	5	0.34

a. In the presence of 0.5 ml of 0.1N potassium tetrachloro mercurate.

b. In the presence of EDTA as masking agent.

It may however be noted that aniline and sulphur dioxide interfere when present in larger amounts.

The procedure reported is a new approach for the determination of nitrite in water. It has been found that nitrogen dioxide in air can be detected up to 0.6 ppm by absorbing contaminated air through acetic acid solution of catechol and developing the colour as described in the procedure. However due to unreliable absorption efficiency of the acidic absorbing medium, the quantitative estimation of nitrogen dioxide in air is not reliable using phenols¹⁰. More studies with similar reagents are required to assess the feasibility of this reaction for pollution studies.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Professor S. G. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing facilities. One of us (A.B.) is thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. W. LIJINSKY and S. EPSTEIN, *Nature*, 1970, **225**, 21.
2. P. MAGRE and J. BARNES, *Br. J. Cancer*, 1956, **10**, 114.
3. Z. KNOTEK and P. SCHMIDT, *Pediatrics*, 1964, **38**, 78.
4. J. E. MCKEE and H. W. WOLF, Resources Agency of California, "Water Quality Criteria", State Water Quality Control Board Publication, 1963, **3(A)**, 224.
5. H. BARNES, *Analyst*, 1950, **75**, 388.
6. J. B. PATE and E. C. TABOR, *Amer. Industr. Hyg. Ass. J.*, 1962, **23**, 145.
7. P. GRIESS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1879, **12**, 427.
8. B. E. SALTZMAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1949.
9. K. TOEI and T. KIYOSE, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1977, **88**, 125.
10. T. NASH, *Atmospheric Environment*, 1970, **4**, 661.
11. C. GELMAN, R. GANSON and H. KLAPPER, Proc. 51st Annual Meeting APCA, Phila., Pa. May, 13, p. 1958.
12. A. K. BABKO and A. T. PILIPENKO, *Photometric Analysis, Methods of Determining Non-Metals*, (Mir Publishers, Moscow), 1974.
13. A. BHATT and V. K. GUPTA, *Intern. J. of Environ. Stud.*, 1979, **14**, 65.
14. H. FREJKA and J. ZIKA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1933, **5**, 253.
15. M. AMAROSA and M. R. CESARONI, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1953, **83**, 853.